

GeoAI-Based Analysis of Spatial Associations Between Access to Specialized Healthcare and Premature Mortality From Respiratory Tract Cancer

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Abstract

Premature mortality from respiratory tract cancer (RTC) remains unevenly distributed across territories, reflecting inequalities in access to specialized healthcare services. This study applied a geographic artificial intelligence (GeoAI) framework to investigate spatially varying associations between healthcare accessibility indicators and premature RTC mortality in Southern Brazil. A population-based ecological study was conducted across 1,191 municipalities using mortality data from 2018–2022. Spatial autocorrelation was assessed using Moran's I and Local Indicators of Spatial Association (LISA). Model performance was compared between Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR), and Geographically Weighted Gradient Boosting Regression (GWRBoost). Spatial block cross-validation was implemented to reduce spatial leakage and overfitting. GWRBoost improved model fit ($R^2 = 0.926$) compared with OLS ($R^2 = 0.053$) and GWR ($R^2 = 0.473$), while reducing residual spatial dependence (Moran's I = -0.048). These findings highlight the potential of geographically weighted spatial machine learning for geographically targeted cancer control strategies.

Keywords: Spatial machine learning; GWRBoost; Spatial accessibility

Published in "Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI 2026) – Poster Papers", edited by Haosheng Huang and Nico Van de Weghe, GeoAI 2026, 3-6 June 2026, Ghent, Belgium.

This contribution underwent single-blind peer review based on the extended abstract.

1. Introduction

Premature mortality from respiratory tract cancer (RTC) remains a major public health challenge worldwide and is unevenly distributed across territories, particularly in regions with heterogeneous access to specialized healthcare services (IARC 2022, WHO 2025). In countries with large territorial and healthcare disparities such as Brazil, geographic differences in diagnostic infrastructure, oncology service availability, and spatial accessibility may contribute to substantial regional inequalities in cancer outcomes (Travassos & Martins 2004).

Conventional global regression approaches frequently assume stationary and predominantly linear relationships between predictors and health outcomes, even though healthcare access and cancer mortality are shaped by complex localized geographic processes (Fotheringham et al. 2002, Nakaya et al. 2005). Consequently, important spatial heterogeneity and nonlinear associations may remain masked when global models are applied to geographically heterogeneous health systems.

Recent advances in geographic artificial intelligence (GeoAI) have enabled the integration of spatial analysis and machine learning to model spatially varying and nonlinear relationships while accounting for geographic dependence structures. Geographically weighted machine learning approaches, such as Geographically Weighted Gradient Boosting Regression (GWRBoost), provide an interpretable framework for identifying localized associations and territorial heterogeneity that are frequently overlooked by conventional global regression models (Wang et al. 2022). This study applied a GeoAI framework based on geographically weighted boosting to investigate spatial associations between specialized healthcare access and premature RTC mortality in Southern Brazil.

2. Methods

2.1. Study area and data

A population-based ecological study was conducted across the 1,191 municipalities of the Southern Region of Brazil, comprising the states of Paraná, Santa Catarina, and Rio Grande do Sul. Premature respiratory tract cancer (RTC) mortality was defined as deaths occurring between 30 and 69 years of age according to World Health Organization criteria (WHO 2025). Mortality data from 2018-2022 were obtained from the Brazilian Mortality Information System (SIM), while population estimates and geographic boundary data were obtained from the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE). After preprocessing and multicollinearity assessment, five indicators related to specialized healthcare access were included in the analysis: radiography procedures rate, bronchoscopy procedures rate, computed tomography procedures rate, biopsy procedures rate, and spatial accessibility to oncology centers. Spatial accessibility to oncology centers was estimated using the Enhanced Two-Step Floating Catchment Area (E2SFCA) method (Luo & Qi 2009).

2.2 Spatial analysis

Premature RTC mortality rates were smoothed using empirical Bayesian estimation to reduce instability in small-area estimates (Anselin 1998). Global spatial autocorrelation was assessed using Moran's I statistic (Moran 1950), while local spatial clustering patterns were evaluated using

Local Indicators of Spatial Association (LISA) (Anselin 1998). The spatial distribution of smoothed mortality rates and local clustering patterns across Southern Brazil are presented in the Figure 1.

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of smoothed premature respiratory tract cancer mortality rates (A) and LISA cluster patterns (B) in Southern Brazil, 2018-2022.

2.3 GeoAI framework

Three modeling approaches were compared: Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR), and Geographically Weighted Gradient Boosting Regression (GWRBoost). GWRBoost was selected because it integrates geographically weighted modeling with nonlinear boosting, allowing the identification of spatially varying relationships while preserving local interpretability (Wang 2022). To reduce risks of spatial leakage and overfitting, spatial block cross-validation based on K-Means clustering was implemented (Roberts et al. 2017, Valavi et al. 2019), partitioning the study area into 10 spatial blocks that iteratively separated training and testing regions. Hyperparameter optimization evaluated combinations of spatial bandwidths, number of boosting learners, and learning rates. Model performance was assessed using Residual Sum of Squares (RSS), Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), adjusted R^2 , and residual Moran's I. Local coefficient significance was estimated using bootstrap-derived standard errors. Given the large number of localized coefficient tests, significance maps were interpreted as exploratory representations of geographically varying associations rather than confirmatory inferential evidence.

3. Results

Global spatial autocorrelation analysis identified moderate positive spatial dependence (Moran's $I = 0.55$), with high-high mortality clusters concentrated mainly in Rio Grande do Sul (Fig. 1).

Marked differences in model performance were observed between global, local, and spatial machine learning approaches (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparison of OLS, GWR, and GWRBoost model performance.

Metric	OLS	GWR	GWRBoost
RSS	147662.91	82225.56	11608.81
AIC	9132.70	8692.05	2731.87
Adjusted R ²	0.049	0.470	0.925
Residual Moran's I	0.510	0.263	-0.048

OLS exhibited limited explanatory performance and substantial residual spatial dependence, indicating poor representation of localized geographic processes. GWR partially improved model fit by accounting for spatial non-stationarity, whereas GWRBoost further improved the representation of geographically heterogeneous relationships while substantially reducing residual spatial autocorrelation.

The high explanatory performance observed in GWRBoost should be interpreted in the context of geographically structured ecological data and the model's capacity to capture nonlinear spatial heterogeneity rather than as evidence of causal prediction. Spatial block cross-validation and residual autocorrelation diagnostics were incorporated to mitigate risks of spatial leakage and overfitting.

Observed and predicted mortality patterns showed strong spatial agreement under GWRBoost, with residuals displaying predominantly random spatial distribution (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Observed mortality rates (A), GWRBoost predicted mortality rates (B), and residual spatial distribution (C) for premature respiratory tract cancer mortality in Southern Brazil, 2018-2022.

Local coefficient maps revealed geographically varying associations between healthcare indicators and mortality. Radiography rates showed the most spatially consistent positive associations, particularly in municipalities of Rio Grande do Sul and parts of Santa Catarina. Tomography, bronchoscopy, biopsy, and oncology accessibility exhibited heterogeneous localized associations, including both positive and negative regional patterns. These findings demonstrate that relationships between specialized healthcare indicators and premature RTC mortality are spatially non-stationary and vary substantially across territories.

4. Discussion

This study demonstrated that geographically weighted spatial machine learning improved the representation of spatially heterogeneous relationships associated with premature RTC mortality compared with both global and conventional local regression approaches.

The limited performance of OLS reinforces the inadequacy of stationary global models for geographically heterogeneous health outcomes (Fotheringham et al. 2002, Nakaya et al. 2005). Although GWR partially accounted for local variation, GWRBoost achieved substantially better fit while minimizing residual spatial dependence, suggesting that geographically weighted boosting may better accommodate nonlinear and spatially adaptive processes commonly observed in territorial health systems (Wang 2022).

An important contribution of this study lies in the interpretability of localized associations. Rather than producing a single global coefficient, the proposed GeoAI framework identified geographically varying relationships between healthcare indicators and mortality patterns, supporting place-based analysis and geographically targeted decision-making.

The widespread positive association observed for radiography rates may reflect areas with higher diagnostic demand, concentration of specialized services, or greater disease burden rather than direct causal effects (Corrêa et al. 2020). Similarly, the heterogeneous associations observed for tomography and oncology accessibility likely reflect regional differences in healthcare organization, healthcare utilization, and territorial infrastructure (Travassos & Martins 2004).

The high explanatory performance observed in GWRBoost should be interpreted in the context of geographically structured ecological data and the model's capacity to capture nonlinear spatial heterogeneity rather than as evidence of causal prediction. In this context, the integration of geographically weighted boosting, spatial block cross-validation, and residual spatial diagnostics represents an important methodological strategy for reducing spatial leakage and improving the robustness of spatial machine learning applications in health research.

This study has limitations inherent to ecological analyses and secondary databases, including potential underreporting, unmeasured confounding, and limitations in healthcare accessibility proxies. Additionally, local coefficient significance patterns should be interpreted as exploratory representations of geographically varying associations rather than confirmatory inferential evidence.

5. Conclusion

GWRBoost improved the representation of spatially heterogeneous associations between specialized healthcare access and premature respiratory tract cancer mortality while reducing residual spatial dependence. These findings highlight the potential of geographically weighted

spatial machine learning to support the identification of territorial health inequalities and geographically targeted cancer control strategies.

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